

Moving On: Managing Data at the End of a Project or Upon Leaving the University

If you have submitted your PhD thesis, completed a research project and/or are leaving the University of Basel, it is essential to address key questions regarding your datasets. We recommend to start planning a few months ahead to ensure your data is transferred and/or stored appropriately. This includes coordinating with your project leader/supervisor and IT services.

Important note: Research data generated within the framework of research projects at the University of Basel generally remain the property of the University of Basel.

Checklist to guide you through the process

Update the Data Management Plan (DMP)

- Ensure the DMP reflects the current status of your data, and future needs such as permissions and access controls for collaborators or supervisors, or long-term storage solutions.

Clean up data on the storage infrastructure

- Copy all personal documents to a private storage.
- Remove redundant files (e.g. drafts and earlier versions of published papers).

Review and enhance data documentation

- Update the README files.
- Compile any additional documentation required to understand and reuse the data.

Identify data that can or must be published

- Consider the legal obligations and the requirements of your funding institutions and publishers.
- Organize the publication of eligible datasets in an appropriate repository.
- Include comprehensive documentation and metadata for published data.

Plan for data preservation

- Check the retention period specified by the university and funding agencies (e.g., the SNSF currently recommends 10 years).
- If applicable, arrange for data deletion after the required retention period.
- Assign a responsible person in charge of long-term data preservation.
- Choose a suitable storage solution for the data to be preserved.
- If you need future data access, discuss access arrangements with your project leader/supervisor and IT.

Organize data transfer

- If data must be transferred, plan and execute the transfer process in coordination with relevant stakeholders.

After having completed these steps, arrange a handover appointment with your project leader/supervisor. Ideally, both parties sign a confirmation that the data have been handed over appropriately. Such a document could also outline agreements regarding future use of the data.

More detailed information can be found in the document on [Management of Digital Research Data at the End of a Project](#), developed by the RDM Network of the University of Basel.

